

**A PRACTICAL COMPARISON OF STANDARD TEST METHODS
USING CARBON FIBRE-REINFORCED EPOXY**

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ABSTRACT

A survey has been carried out covering the recommended standard test methods published by several international organisations. The particular test methods under consideration are tensile, flexure and short beam shear, appropriate for fibre-reinforced composite materials. Although there is a fair degree of overlap from one organisation to another, significant inconsistencies exist in many areas. Tests carried out to match the recommendations of each standards authority allow direct comparison of results. These tests have been conducted on specimens machined from laminates of a carbon fibre-reinforced epoxy, the laminates being prepared with several stacking sequences. The results indicate that the practical differences between the various test methods give subtle, rather than glaring, discrepancies, which in many cases are not statistically significant.

INTRODUCTION

The use of advanced composite materials in increasingly demanding applications, requires test data which designers can rely upon implicitly in the design process. The acquisition of reliable test data, suitable for use in design, presupposes a test method capable of producing such data. There are, of course, several highly respected standards organisations which publish advised test procedures for almost every conceivable requirement. It is to their credit that, in general at

least, these organisations recognise the need to review their recommendations in the light of the particular requirements of the advanced composite industry.

Many companies solve their specific problems by the introduction of "in-house" standards. This approach must be applauded, since successful methods frequently become generally accepted, and eventually receive the stamp of official approval. It is not, however, in the area of a particular company's needs that updating of standard test methods is required, as far as advanced composites are concerned. There is, at the present time, widespread dissatisfaction with very basic test methods recommended by different internationally recognised standards organisations. In the U.K. this concern has surfaced in the form of a discussion document [1] which puts the case for improved standardised test methods for tensile, flexural and interlaminar shear data acquisition for advanced composite materials.

Given the general interest in these primary areas of design data test method definition, it seems appropriate to carry out a comparison of such test methods currently recommended by some of the major standards institutions. A full appraisal of the range of possible variables would, of course, be prohibitively expensive. The programme of work presented here does, however, consider several types of laminate lay-up in carbon fibre-reinforced epoxy (CFRE), tested in tensile, flexural and short beam shear modes. These tests were carried out to reflect the recommendations of the American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM), the British Standards Institute (BSI), and the Composites Research Advisory Group (CRAG).

TESTING PROGRAMME

Materials and laminates

The material used throughout this investigation was Ciba-Geigy unidirectional XAS carbon, prepregged with 914 epoxy resin. Laminates were autoclave cured to the manufacturers' specified cure schedule to give unidirectional and multidirectional plates of thickness 1 mm and 2 mm. The ply thickness was approximately 0.125 mm so that 1 mm and 2 mm laminates consisted of 8 and 16 plies respectively. Table 1 gives the actual stacking sequences involved.

TABLE 1. Laminate lay-ups investigated

Stacking Sequence	
1 mm thick	2 mm thick
(0/0/0/0) _s	(0/0/0/0) _{2s}
(+45/0/-45/0) _s	(+45/0/-45/0) _{2s}
(0/90/0/90) _s	(0/90/0/90) _{2s}
(90/+45/0/-45) _s	(90/+45/0/-45) _{2s}
(+45/-45/+45/-45) _s	(+45/-45/+45/-45) _{2s}

The laminated plates, once cured, were machined dry to the required specimen dimensions using a diamond impregnated circular wheel saw, with final edge finishing being achieved with fine emery paper.

Test methods

For a full description of the test methods used it is necessary to refer to the particular specifications of the organisations involved. The CRAG recommendations are all contained within a single discussion document [1]; the relevant ASTM specifications are for tensile [2], flexure [3] and interlaminar shear [4]; and the closest BSI standards for the same modes of measurement are given in [5 - 7] respectively.

Sottos [8] presents a comparative review for each type of test as recommended by the three institutes, and points out many of the inconsistencies involved. In some cases specifications are not available which address specifically the high modulus, high strength composites currently in use. It is also noted that the ASTM and BSI specifications tend to be written in a way which allows a fair degree of freedom of choice, in order to apply over a wider range of circumstances. The CRAG recommendations are, on the whole, more specific, with limited options available.

Without referring directly to any particular type of test, there are differences between the recommendations of the organisations involved here on almost every point. It should be added, however, that in many cases, given the degree of freedom offered within each specification, overlap is frequently possible.

As far as tensile testing is concerned, there are differences between the methods suggested in the areas of specimen dimensions, end tab material, length, thickness and means of preparation; method of strain measurement; approach used for modulus determination; and the definition of testing speed. In addition CRAG [1] uses different specimen shapes for unidirectionally oriented fibre composites, dependent upon whether design, or quality control data is sought. In a similar way the BSI [5] differentiate between unidirectionally oriented materials, and those with multiple orientations. ASTM [2] ignores such delicacies and uses constant cross-section, parallel-sided specimens throughout. Figure 1 shows the various specimen shapes encountered, and therefore tested, in this programme, Table 2 lists the actual specimen dimensions and testing conditions used for each standard.

For flexure tests there is no involvement with end tabs, or changes in specimen shape, although there are dimensional differences between the three standards. Each organisation offers the three-point bending approach, with ASTM [3] also allowing the four-point arrangement. ASTM also has the option of several span-to-thickness ratios, whilst BSI [6] offers just one, CRAG [1] allows ratios dependent upon fibre type and lay-up. There are also significant differences in the dimensions recommended for the support and loading rollers. Figure 2 shows the three and four-point loading arrangements, and defines the dimensions given in Table 3 for all of the flexure tests carried out here.

Figure 1. Tensile specimen shapes and dimensions.
 (a) ASTM, (b) BSI, (c) CRAG.

TABLE 2. Dimensions and test conditions adopted for tensile tests.

	ASTM		BSI		CRAG	
	UNI	MULTI	UNI	MULTI	UNI	MULTI
t_o	1,2	2	2	1,2	1,2	1,2
t	-	-	1	-	1	-
L	120	120	100	100	100	100
W	12.7	25.4	10	25	10	25
A	2	2	3	3	2	2
L_1	40	40	50	50	50	50
End tag material	0/90 E-glass composite		Al bonded before machining specimen		Al	
End tag profile	5°		-		-	

All dimensions in mm and test speed 5 mm per minute.

Figure 2. Arrangements used for flexure tests.
(a) 3-point bending, (b) 4-point bending.

TABLE 3. Dimensions and test conditions adopted for flexure tests.

	W	t	s/t	L	d ₁	d ₂	Test speed (mm/min)
	25	2	16	50	6.4	6.4	0.85
ASTM	"	"	32	80	"	"	3.4
	"	"	40*+	100	"	"	5.3
	"	1	" +	60	"	"	2.7
BSI	15	2	16 +	60	4	10	1.0
CRAG	10	2	40 +	100	10	25	5.0

* also used for 4-pt bend, same dimensions.

+ also used for specimens with multi-axially aligned fibres.
all dimensions in mm.

In all cases the recommended arrangement for the inter-laminar shear test is a short beam in three-point bending. So that the set-up is similar to that shown in Figure 2 (a), but with a small s/t ratio. Table 4 indicates the dimensions adopted for these tests, the only differences being in the recommended length of the test-piece, the roller diameters, and the definition of testing rate.

TABLE 4. Dimensions and test conditions adopted for interlaminar short beam shear tests.

	W	t	s/t	L	d ₁	d ₂	Test speed (mm/min)
ASTM	10	2	5	14	3.2	6.35	1.3
BSI	"	"	"	12	6	6	1.0
CRAG	"	"	"	20	"	"	1.0

All dimensions in mm.

The tests reported here were carried out precisely to the published specification, and the options available within those specifications, with the exception of the ASTM tensile tests. For these tests small deviations from the recommended longitudinal dimensions were necessary, due to material limitations.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

All of the data shown in Tables 5-7 indicate mean values for tests on five specimens, the numbers suggested by the various standards. The tensile results in Table 5 show both elastic modulus and ultimate strength being dependent upon lay-up, in particular the proportion of unidirectional fibres. Within each laminate type, the results for the different test standards show variations which are not systematic in any way. The variations which exist are largely covered by the scatter bands associated with each batch of specimens. One point which should

be made, however, is that for unidirectional lay-up specimens, with waists machined at mid length, the modulus recorded is noticeably higher than for plain specimens of the same lay-up. It is, perhaps, not surprising that an effect is noted, considering the difficulties introduced by machining away half the specimen thickness. The tensile strength results for the waisted specimens are also higher than for non-waisted specimens, suggesting that the outer surfaces of the laminates are slightly resin rich. Whilst failures for these unidirectional lay-ups were predominately within the gauge length, plain specimens tended to shatter, splitting longitudinally, whereas waisted specimens were constrained to fail within the waist, and with little evidence of gross splitting. The 0/90 oriented samples had very clean fractures straight across the specimen width. These fractures occurred largely within the gauge length, with the exception of the ASTM specimens, which failed under the glass composite end tabs. Essentially the same pattern emerged for the multi-directional lay-ups. Even though BSI and CRAG specimens for these lay-ups contained no central waisting, they still tended to fracture near the centre, whereas ASTM specimens invariably failed under the end tabs.

TABLE 5. Tensile test results.

Test	Spec thickness (mm)	Fibre orient	Tensile modulus (GPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)
ASTM	1	UNI	141 ± 4%	1890 ± 12%
CRAG	1	"	142 ± 3.7%	1860 ± 8.7%
ASTM	2	"	143 ± 7.8%	1980 ± 5.4%
BSI	2*	"	166 ± 6.1%	2050 ± 5.4%
CRAG	2*	"	154 ± 14%	2090 ± 6.3%
BSI	1	0/90	76.5 ± 7%	1080 ± 6.3%
CRAG	"	"	79.5 ± 6.8%	1000 ± 14%
ASTM	2	"	76.8 ± 5.7%	963 ± 8.3%
BSI	2	"	73.8 ± 12%	1010 ± 4.7%
CRAG	"	"	77.6 ± 2.9%	1110 ± 6.6%
BSI	1	90/+0/-	55.9 ± 1.3%	762 ± 8.3%
CRAG	"	"	51.8 ± 6.6%	748 ± 6.5%
ASTM	2	"	53.6 ± 6.6%	680 ± 4.4%
BSI	"	"	45.6 ± 7.3%	777 ± 4.1%
CRAG	"	"	58.2 ± 3.4%	800 ± 7.2%
BSI	1	+0/-/0	77.5 ± 10%	1180 ± 10%
CRAG	"	"	81 ± 9.7%	1210 ± 8.4%

* waisted specimen t = 1 mm (see Fig. 1)

Flexural modulus and strength were also, as expected, found to be dependent upon lay-up, in the same way as the tensile data. These results are shown in Table 6. For the unidirectional lay-up several points are worth noting. Firstly, for ASTM 3-point bend tests, a very low value of modulus was obtained for span-to-depth ratio = 16, whereas results for higher ratios were not only increased, but almost identical. A similar discrepancy was noted for the BSI data at this low span-to-depth ratio, although the multi-directional lay-ups showed no effect.

TABLE 6. Flexure results.

Test	Thickness (mm)	s/t	Fibre orient	Flexural modulus (GPa)	Flexural strength (MPa)
ASTM-3pt	2	16	Uni	59 ± 5%	1370 ± 4.1%
"	"	32	"	103 ± 4.2%	1440 ± 3.2%
"	"	40	"	102 ± 4.4%	1490 ± 7.3%
"	1	40	"	104 ± 5.7%	1890 ± 4%
ASTM-4pt	2	40	"	132 ± 7.7%	2550 ± 4.6%
BSI-3pt	2	16	"	73.7 ± 7%	1460 ± 5.3%
CRAG-3pt	2	40	"	115 ± 1.9%	1720 ± 6.4%
ASTM-3pt	1	40	0/90	66.9 ± 8.8%	1078 ± 4.5%
"	2	40	"	50.7 ± 5.5%	968 ± 3.7%
BSI-3pt	2	16	"	52.8 ± 3.4%	1160 ± 16%
CRAG-3pt	2	40	"	57.4 ± 2.1%	1010 ± 7.8%
ASTM-3pt	2	40	90/+ / 0/-	58.8 ± 1.5%	964 ± 1.8%
BSI-3pt	2	16	"	48.7 ± 6.9%	993 ± 2.7%
CRAG-3pt	2	40	"	62.8 ± 4.6%	923 ± 3.5%
ASTM-3pt	1	40	+/- / +/-	26.1 ± 4.6%	635 ± 6.0%
"	2	40	"	19.1 ± 1.7%	446 ± 13%
ASTM-4pt	2	40	"	24.4 ± 3.1%	550 ± 7.3%
BSI-3pt	2	16	"	19.4 ± 1.6%	478 ± 4%
CRAG-3pt	2	40	"	16.9 ± 3.9%	216 ± 1.8%

The failure mode recorded for all of these low span-to-depth ratio specimens was one of cracking and crushing, on the compression side of the sample, under the central loading roller. Again for unidirectional lay-ups, CRAG gave relatively high results for modulus and strength compared with those from ASTM tests. The major differences between the tests are roller diameters and specimen width. Considering the large differences in these parameters, significant discrepancies in the results might well be expected, although the failure mode was identical, with fracture occurring under the central loading roller. For the remaining lay-ups discrepancies between CRAG and ASTM results are not so

marked and all fail by tension side cracking under the central roller. Two points remain to be made: ASTM 3-point bend specimens where beam thickness is only 1 mm tend to give high failure strengths; and the ASTM 4-point bend appears to give significantly high values for both modulus and strength.

Turning finally to the interlaminar shear results of Table 7, a similar trend is noted as for the tensile and flexure tests, that the proportion of unidirectionally oriented fibres influences the strength of the laminate. There is remarkably good agreement between the different standard test methods as indicated in Table 4, and this carries over in the results. All of the mean values for a particular lay-up being within quite close limits. What is noticeable, however, is that the scatter of results within a group of specimens is relatively high for those lay-ups with 25% or less 0° plies, irrespective of test method.

TABLE 7. Interlaminar shear strength results

Test	Fibre orient	ILSS (MPa)
ASTM	Uni	94.0 ± 5.5%
BSI	"	96.0 ± 2.7%
CRAG	"	98.8 ± 5.8%
ASTM	0/90	80.3 ± 2.8%
BSI	"	74.3 ± 5.8%
CRAG	"	82.0 ± 3.8%
ASTM	90/+0/0/-	65.0 ± 13%
BSI	"	69.0 ± 16%
CRAG	"	57.0 ± 13%
ASTM	+0/-/0	76.1 ± 1.8%
BSI	"	80.6 ± 3.2%
CRAG	"	77.2 ± 4.5%
ASTM	+/-/+/-	48.0 ± 11%
BSI	"	52.8 ± 5.9%
CRAG	"	47.4 ± 9%

CONCLUSIONS

The purpose of this work was to carry out a comparison of basic property data obtained using the recommendations of several standards organisations. Since the specifications used all suggest that only five specimens are required to obtain a reliable result, this was the number tested in each case. Such a small sample does, however, pose severe limitations on the statistical analyses that can be meaningfully employed. As a result no serious statistical manipulations have been attempted. The results from each test method are simply presented as a

mean of the five data points together with the associated standard deviation divided by the mean, and expressed as a percentage. It is envisaged that further work will be done in the future to compare testing standards further, and that large populations should be studied at that stage. An overview of the results included in this report suggests that, with one or two exceptions, the different standards do, in fact, give data which are probably not significantly different. The exceptions worthy of note are: the differences obtained when tensile specimens are waisted centrally, as opposed to testing uniform sections; and results from low s/t ratio flexure tests.

Whilst the actual data obtained may not for the most part show glaring differences, there are very good arguments for the complete harmonisation of standard test methods. The tests carried out here, whilst conforming to different test standards, have been influenced by a desire for a certain degree of uniformity. So that where options are available within a given specification, and the options available are often quite wide, a single option has been chosen common to each of the standards. It is difficult to imagine to what degree the results would have changed had extreme values been chosen. This is, perhaps, an area which could benefit from further study. It does appear, however, that the CRAG recommendations have moved in the right direction. Although their suggested standards reflect many of the features of the BSI standards, they are aimed specifically at high performance composite materials, and the options available within the specifications are quite limited.

One particular problem associated with the ASTM tensile testing procedure appears to be a poor recommendation for end tab material. Using the glass composite material suggested, the experience here was a high incidence of failure under the end tabs. Unfortunately, it is not possible to be unequivocal on this point as the specimens were slightly shorter than those recommended. It is not thought, however, that such a discrepancy is likely to be the major cause of such failures. Fractures of this type were not a feature of BSI or CRAG tests where aluminium tabs were used, and specimens were, in fact, shorter. It appears that the ASTM tab material is at fault, and could usefully be reconsidered.

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